

Multiple Imputation, Machine Learning, and Hot Deck Imputation Models with the 2021 National Survey on Drug Use and Health (NSDUH)

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Abstract: This study will evaluate multiple imputation and machine learning imputation strategies, as well as a novel natural language processing (NLP) deep neural network algorithm and hot deck NLP algorithm vis-à-vis hot deck imputation strategies and complete case analysis (i.e., listwise deletion) on artificially created missing-at-random (MAR) 2021 NSDUH survey data. Missing rates are 1.43% ($n=1,000$), 9% ($n=6400$), and 16% ($n=11,200$). The goal of this study is to evaluate several imputation methods and propose a novel NLP approach to imputation.

Key words: Machine learning, Imputation, NSDUH 2021, Natural Language Processing (NLP)

1 Introduction

Missing values are a persistent problem in survey data, with incompleteness often leading to biased estimates and faulty statistical inferences. Over the years several methods for missing values imputation (MVI) have been proposed, with Rubin (1996) proposing that m multiple plausible values be assigned to a single missing unit to account for uncertainty of the missing value. Recently machine-learning (ML) techniques have gained in popularity (Thomas and Rajabi, 2021), which are algorithmic-based models that iteratively “learn” the data often with the goal to produce maximum accuracy (Breiman, 2001). Hot deck imputation is another popular method where missing values from one or more variables (called the *recipient*) are matched with observed values from a *donor* having complete cases and similar to the *recipient* on a number of crossed covariates. Andridge and Little (2010) found that since hot deck methods do not rely on model fitting for imputation, they are less sensitive to model misspecification compared to parametric models. Current classifications for missingness are based on Rubin’s (1976) three mechanisms: missing completely at random (MCAR), missing at random (MAR), and missing not at random (MNAR), also referred to NMAR in the literature. Since MCAR is missing randomly, several imputation techniques, including mean imputation, are sufficient. MAR defines the probability of missing related to other observed covariates, while for MNAR the probability of missing varies for reasons that are unknown. Missing between 1-5% are consider trivial and manageable; 5-15% requires refined methods; and 15% and more impact prediction and inferences (Moothy et al., 2014).

2 Method

2.1 Purpose

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the performance of two NLP models and several multiple imputation models, including two algorithm-based ML imputation models, compared to complete case analysis (i.e., listwise deletion), survey- and non-survey weighted random sample hot deck procedures, and a weighted sequential hot deck procedure. Metrics for evaluation include empirical bias (EBias), root mean square error (RMSE), % coverage, and, popular in machine-learning community, percentage of correct prediction (PCP) (Thomas and Rajabi, 2021).

2.2 Sample

The survey data for this analysis is from the 2021 National Survey on Drug Use and Health (NSDUH). Variables for analysis include several demographic variables (e.g., age, ethnicity, education level, insured status) as well as several substance use variables (e.g. substance use treatment received, illicit drug use in past month, smoking tobacco in past month, alcohol in past month). There were multivariate missing on 5 variables.

2.3 Study Design

MAR missing was artificially induced on 1.43% ($n=1,000$), 9 % ($n=6,400$), and 16% ($n=11,200$) of the observations in the variable alcohol past month (**ALCMON**) using algorithm adapted from van Buuren (2012). Survey weighted and non-survey weighted hot deck imputation methods were used PROC SURVEYIMPUTE in SAS 9.4 incorporating the full set of covariates. A weighted sequential hot deck (WSHD) method was also performed on a select number of covariates using SUDAAN version 11.0. Multiple imputation ML procedures were implemented in R version 4.3.2 using the packages `mixgb` (Deng, 2023) and `mice` (van Buuren and Groothuis-Oudshoorn, 2011) packages. The theory of multiple imputation by chained equations (“mice”) is described in van Buuren (2012). CART and XGBOOST multiple imputation classification and regression tree and gradient boosted tree algorithms were utilized (Deng and Lumley, 2023). A novel approach using the natural language processing (NLP) deep neural network BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) algorithm was also utilized. Since October 2020, BERT algorithm has been used by Google for virtually every English-based search query (Schwartz, 2020). To use BERT, NSDUH numeric values were transformed into data labels (e.g., 0 equals “No”, 1 equals “Yes”). Data labels permit a more nuanced approach to data analysis, where categories formerly designated missing, such as “Refused to answer”, “I don’t know”, “Intentionally left blank”, now provide meaningful information. Responses are strung together as a sentence, and BERT predicts “Yes” or “No” to “Alcohol used past month” based on supervised learning model. A hot deck version of the BERT model was also used, in which *recipient* and *donor* cases were matched based on the BERT probability of endorsing “alcohol use past month”.

2.4 Data Analysis Plan

The following models were evaluated based on multivariate missing data with artificially induced missing rates on the variable **ALCMON** of 1.43% ($n=1,000$), 9% ($n=6,400$), and 16% ($n=11,200$): complete cases (i.e., listwise deletion), survey- and non-survey weighted hot deck procedures in SAS, a weighted sequential hot deck procedure in SUDAAN, multiple imputation by chained equations (“mice”) in R, multiple imputation with classification and regression trees (i.e., “CART”) and multiple imputation with a gradient boosted trees using `mixgb` package in R, and a novel NLP BERT and BERT hot deck algorithm implemented using `ktrain` package in

Python. Hyperparameters for the XGBOOST model were determined through cross-validation. Evaluation metrics include empirical bias (EBias), root mean square error (RMSE), percentage of correct prediction (PCP), and coverage. EBias and RMSE are defined as follows:

$$EBias = \frac{1}{1000} \sum_{i=1}^{1000} (\hat{\theta}_i - \theta) \quad (1)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{1000} \sum_{i=1}^{1000} (\hat{\theta}_i - \theta)^2} \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{\theta}_i$ is the estimated prevalence estimate from the i^{th} sample of 1000 Monte Carlo iterations and θ is the true prevalence value of “alcohol past month”. Coverage is the percent of instances in which the true θ is within the 95% confidence interval in 1000 bootstrapped samples.

3 Results

Table 1 evaluates of the performance of the imputation models on various metrics. For all the missing rates, the BERT NLP model had the best percentage of correct prediction (PCP) at slightly over 80% and best coverage at 1.43% missing. The lowest empirical bias (EBias) and RMSE for 1.43% was with the WSHD model. The lowest EBias and RMSE for 16% missing rates was the multiple imputation classification and regression tree (micart) model. This also had the greatest coverage at 16% missing. The BERT Hot Deck model had the lowest EBias and tied with the multiple imputation by chained equations (mice) model for lowest RMSE at 9% missing. The survey weighted and unweighted hot deck models were only comparable to the other models at 1.43% missing.

4 Discussion

This study explored several ML imputation strategies in conjunction with hot deck imputation strategies and a novel approach using a natural language processing (NLP) algorithm and a hot deck version of NLP. All the methods were comparable when missingness was relatively trivial, though at higher levels the multiple imputation and BERT hot deck models were optimal though the WSHD did quite well. A limitation of the study is that the WSHD method used only a subset of covariates whereas the other models used all the covariates. This study provides evidence of effective imputation strategies for large survey data. Further exploration of NLP techniques for MVI, particularly hot deck NLP, may be warranted given its comparability with other high-performing imputation strategies.

Table 1: Evaluation of Several Imputation Methods on NSDUH 2021 data, by Missing Rates

Method	EBias	RMSE	PCP (%)	Coverage %
1.43% missing ($n=1,000$)				
complete cases	.001532	.001921	N/A	95.5
survey weighted hot deck	.001755	.002183	50.5	91.6
non-survey weighted hot deck	.001690	.002109	50.6	93.4
weighted sequential hot deck (wshd)	.001505	.001888	71.6	95.5
MI chained equations (mice)	.001514	.001899	75.2	95.4
MI classification regression trees (cart)	.001513	.001898	75.9	95.3
MI xgboost (mixgb)	.001514	.001896	76.5	95.5
BERT NLP model	.001530	.001918	80.0	95.8
BERT Hot Deck NLP model	.001509	.001893	65.2	95.2
Method	EBias	RMSE	PCP (%)	Coverage %
9% missing ($n=6,400$)				
complete cases	.002419	.002913	N/A	79.3
survey weighted hot deck	.006057	.006344	50.1	10.8
non-survey weighted hot deck	.005942	.006235	50.1	12.8
weighted sequential hot deck (wshd)	.001855	.002295	70.5	89.5
MI chained equations (mice)	.001513	.001897	75.1	95.6
MI classification regression trees (cart)	.001534	.001924	75.8	95.3
MI xgboost (mixgb)	.001522	.001909	75.9	95.3
BERT NLP model	.001808	.002246	80.5	91.0
BERT Hot Deck NLP model	.001512	.001897	75.2	94.9
Method	EBias	RMSE	PCP (%)	Coverage %
16% missing ($n=11,200$)				
complete cases	.004678	.005093	N/A	38.2
survey weighted hot deck	.011782	.011932	50.1	0
non-survey weighted hot deck	.011997	.012146	49.2	0
weighted sequential hot deck (wshd)	.002945	.003405	72.1	69.9
MI chained equations (mice)	.001571	.001966	74.3	94.7
MI classification regression trees (cart)	.001531	.001917	75.3	95.2
MI xgboost (mixgb)	.001695	.002122	75.7	93.6
BERT NLP model	.003057	.003513	80.3	67.5
BERT Hot Deck NLP model	.001600	.002004	74.2	94.2

Note. MI are multiple imputation models; NLP is natural language processing. **Bold** estimates are best category estimates.

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Supplemental Materials

Functions for performing the **mice** and machine learning imputation in R as well as R functions for creating MAR missing and hot deck imputation for the NLP model are available at <https://github.com/mvbrow/JSM2024>.